

1 ***Spilocaea oleagina* in Olive Groves of Southern Spain: Survival, Inoculum**
2 **Production, and Dispersal**

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10 **ABSTRACT**

11 Viruega, J. R., Moral, J., Roca, L. F., Navarro, N., and Trapero, A. 2013. *Spilocaea*
12 *oleagina* in olive groves of southern Spain: survival, inoculum production, and
13 dispersal. Plant Dis. 97: XXX-XXX.

14 Olive scab caused by the mitosporic fungus *Spilocaea oleagina* is the most important
15 foliar disease of olive tree. Limited information is available on pathogen survival and
16 disease epidemiology, but such information is essential for development of new control
17 strategies. Pathogen survival and inoculum production on infected olive leaves and
18 conidia dispersal were evaluated during 4 years in an olive orchard of the susceptible
19 cv. Picual in southern Spain. Infected leaves in the tree canopy were important for
20 pathogen survival and conidia production. The number of conidia per cm² of scab lesion
21 and their viability varied greatly among seasons and years; conidia density in lesions
22 was highest (about 1 to 5 × 10⁵ conidia cm⁻²) from November to February in favorable
23 years. This density declined sharply in other periods of the year (becoming zero in
24 summer) or in less favorable years. On fallen leaves, the pathogen did not form new
25 conidia on scab lesions, although some pseudothecia-like structures and

1 chlamydospores were detected. Under humid conditions, the pathogen rapidly
2 disappeared on fallen leaves because the leaves were colonized by saprophytic fungi.
3 The dispersal of conidia as a function of distance from infected leaves in the tree canopy
4 was well described by an exponential model, which together with the lack of conidia in
5 a Burkard spore trap showed that conidia were mainly rain-splash dispersed. Some
6 trapped conidia were attached to olive leaf trichomes, suggesting that detached
7 trichomes might enhance wind dispersal of conidia.

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9 *Additional keywords: Olea europaea, Fusicladium oleagineum, spore dispersal,*
10 *quantitative epidemiology.*

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INTRODUCTION

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The fungus *Spilocaea oleagina* (syn. *Fusicladium oleagineum*) is the causal agent of olive (*Olea europaea*) scab, which is the most important leaf disease of this crop worldwide (15,25,30,41,47). The disease is also called peacock spot because the pathogen produces circular, muddy green to almost black lesions with a chlorotic halo on the abaxial surface of the leaf (1,15). The lesions change from a typical black scab during the winter–spring to a whitish scab during the summer when the cuticle is separated from epidermal cells on infected leaves (15,43). Lesions can also occur along the main vein on the abaxial leaf surface and on leaf petioles, fruit, and fruit peduncles (1,15,45). Most infected leaves and fruit fall to the ground. Olive oil obtained from fallen fruit is of poor quality because various saprophytic fungi colonize the fruit and change the acidity and organoleptic characteristics of the oil (1). Olive scab is mainly controlled by a combination of sanitation and cultural measures, and by applications of

1 copper-based fungicides; correct timing of fungicides is essential for effective control
2 (34,35,41,42).

3 Decisions about the need for pesticide applications in an integrated pest
4 management program are generally based on knowledge of local (in-field) inoculum
5 levels, which are determined by scouting, modeling, and field studies (4,5). Overall,
6 researchers have accepted that *S. oleagina* does not produce sexual spores (ascospores)
7 and that epidemics therefore depend on the numbers of asexual spores (conidia) that are
8 available (15,42). The seasonal and yearly variation in conidial production, however, is
9 poorly understood.

10 Because the Mediterranean climate is characterized by very long, dry and hot
11 summers and mild to cool, wet winters, the summer is the unfavorable sessions for the
12 aerial fungi of olive in this region. Several authors have determined that *S. oleagina*
13 oversummers as mycelium in infected leaves that remain in the tree canopy (15,16,41).
14 In autumn, mycelia resume growth from the latent infections or from old lesions and
15 develops new conidia, which are dispersed by rain drops and run-off (1,15,25,36,41).
16 According to other authors, however, the most important inoculum sources are infected
17 leaves that have fallen to the soil surface (3,17,20). Moreover, Miller (25) indicated that
18 the presence of other saprophytic fungi on the olive leaves affects conidial production
19 by *S. oleagina*. The epidemiological roles of fallen leaves and of saprophytic fungi on
20 olive scab are unknown in Spain.

21 Knowledge of dispersal distance and factors affecting the spread of conidia is
22 essential for management of olive scab and other diseases involving conidia. For a
23 local-lesion disease spread by airborne spores, the amount of diseased plant tissue
24 typically decreases rapidly with increasing distance from a focus (source) of infection,
25 because of a rapid decrease in the aerial spore concentration and deposition on plants

1 with increasing distance from a source of inoculum (4,5,14). The dispersal distance and
2 its response to weather conditions have not been reported for olive scab as it has been
3 for similar pathogens, such as *Venturia inaequalis* and *V. pirina* (4,18,23,39).

4 A better understanding of seasonal patterns of the production and dispersal of
5 the *S. oleagina* conidia could improve management decisions in general and the timing
6 of fungicide applications in particular. Consequently, the main objective of this study
7 was to increase our understanding of olive scab epidemiology by monitoring conidial
8 production on infected aerial and fallen leaves and conidial dispersal distance under
9 field conditions. Preliminary results of this work have been reported (44).

10 MATERIALS AND METHODS

11 **Olive orchard.** The experimental orchard was located in a flat, uniform, 1.2-ha
12 field at the Institute for Research and Formation in Agriculture and Fishery (IFAPA in
13 Spanish), Alameda del Obispo, Córdoba (37.5°N, 4.8°W, altitude 110 m), Andalusia
14 region, southern Spain. The orchard has a Typic Xerofluvent soil with a sandy-loam
15 texture. The climate is Mediterranean, with most rainfall (95%) occurring from October
16 to May. The trees in the orchard were drip irrigated. The experimental orchard was
17 managed according to the principles of commercial olive production in Andalusia (9).
18 Copper-based fungicides (copper sulphate, 3.5 kg Cu per ha) were applied during the
19 spring and autumn to limit fungal foliar and fruit diseases (41).

20 **Survival on aerial or fallen infected leaves.** A total of 600 fallen olive leaves
21 with scab lesions were collected in the Córdoba, Jaén, and Málaga provinces of
22 Andalusia during September–October. Five hundred leaves were placed in 10 nylon-
23 mesh bags (18 × 18 cm with 2-mm openings; 50 leaves per bag) that were placed on the
24 soil surface under the canopies of 5 trees (2 bags per tree). The remaining 100 leaves
25 were incubated in five moist chambers (22 × 16 × 10 cm; 20 leaves per chamber)

1 between two layers of moistened filter paper at $10 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ under dark. One nylon bag or
2 moist chamber was collected weekly, and each leaf was carefully examined at $\times 100$
3 magnification with a compound microscope (Nikon Eclipse 80i; Nikon Corp., Tokyo) to
4 detect fungal structures including potential sexual fruiting bodies (pseudothecia) of *S.*
5 *oleagina*. Moreover, three discs (5 mm diameter) per leaf were mounted on glass slides
6 and stained with acid fuchsin in lactophenol (50 mg l^{-1}). The entire disc was scanned at
7 $\times 400$ magnifications, and conidia were identified and counted.

8 Additionally, 100 leaves (these leaves are hereafter referred to as aerial leaves) showing
9 typical whitish spots that appear after summer (43) were collected from the canopy of
10 the trees during September. The leaves were incubated in four moist chambers in dark
11 growth chambers with alternating $20/12^\circ\text{C}$ daily temperatures and a 14-h photoperiod
12 (45). One moist chamber was collected weekly, and each leaf was carefully examined as
13 described above to detect *S. oleagina* pseudothecia or spores. The study of fallen and
14 aerial leaves was carried out in 1995 and again in 1997.

15 To confirm the observations made on fallen leaves in the experimental orchard, a
16 survey study was conducted in the main olive-growing areas of Andalusia. Fallen olive
17 leaves with scab lesions that had wintered on the soil surface under the tree canopy were
18 collected at the end of the winter in 1996 and 1998. Each year, 50 samples (20 fallen
19 leaves per sample) were examined microscopically for the presence of *S. oleagina*
20 structures or spores as described above.

21 **Conidial density and viability on aerial or fallen infected leaves.** During three
22 consecutive growing seasons (from November 1993 to September 1997), 70
23 symptomatic leaves were arbitrarily removed from each of three trees every 2 weeks in
24 the experimental orchard; leaves were collected from different trees on each sampling
25 date. Forty leaves were individually attached to a glass microscope slide ($26 \times 76 \text{ mm}$)

1 using double-sided adhesive tape (Scotch, clear transparent, 3M Company, MN) each
2 date. The conidia on the leaves were stained with acid fuchsin in lactophenol, and the
3 number of conidia in a part of a lesion ($5 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mm}^2$) was determined at $\times 400$
4 magnifications (12). Because 120 leaves were examined on each date, the number of
5 conidia in a total lesion area of 0.6 mm^2 was determined on each date.

6 To study conidial viability, we used the rest 30 leaves to obtain a suspension of
7 10^5 conidia ml^{-1} . One 5- μl drop of the conidial suspension was placed on each of two
8 microscope coverslips ($20 \times 20 \text{ mm}$) to test germination of conidia. The coverslips
9 (suspension side up) were placed in Petri dishes containing water agar (WA). The
10 dishes, which served as humidity chambers, were kept in the dark at 15°C for 48 h.
11 Conidial germination was stopped by staining with acid fuchsin in lactophenol, and the
12 percentage of conidia that germinated was determined by observing 50 conidia selected
13 at random on each coverslip. A conidium was considered germinated if the germ tube
14 length was at least one-half the length of the longitudinal axis of the conidium. For each
15 date, the trial was performed four times.

16 A similar study was conducted using infected leaves placed on the soil surface
17 under the canopies of several trees in the experimental orchard. The leaves had been
18 previously placed in 10 nylon-mesh bags ($18 \times 18 \text{ cm}$ with 2-mm openings, 50 leaves
19 per bag), and the bags were placed on the soil surface. Conidial density and viability of
20 50 leaves (one bag) were assessed every two weeks for three months or so. The study
21 was carried out during different periods of three consecutive years: March 1995,
22 November 1996, and April 1997.

23 **Fungal diversity on aerial and fallen infected leaves.** We studied the
24 biodiversity of fungi on olive leaves by examination of mycelium or spores on 100
25 leaves from the tree canopy and 100 fallen leaves. The aerial and fallen leaves were

1 separately placed in 0.25-liter Erlenmeyer flasks with 150 ml of sterile water with 1.5
2 ml of Tween® 20 per liter. To remove mycelium or spores, we placed the flasks in an
3 ultrasonic bath (Selecta, Barcelona, Spain) for 10 min, and 100 µl of six serial dilutions
4 (1, 1/2, 1/10, 1/40, 1/200, and 1/400) of each sample were separately cultivated on five
5 media in Petri dishes at $23 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ under fluorescent lights (12-h photoperiod, $350 \mu\text{mol}$
6 $\text{m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$). For each sample (fallen and aerial leaves) and dilution, there were two dishes
7 containing each of the following media: WA, WA acidified with lactic acid [2.5 ml of a
8 25% (vol/vol) per liter of medium], potato dextrose agar (PDA), PDA acidified with
9 lactic acid, and malt extract agar (MEA) (12). To obtain pure cultures, we transferred
10 hyphal tips from the colonies of the fungi to dishes with fresh APDA that were
11 incubated as described above until colonies were large enough to be examined. All
12 isolates were characterized morphologically according to color, growth, and presence or
13 absence of conidiomata after 14 days of growth (Table 1). The length and width of 20
14 conidia per isolate were also measured, and their color, shape, and septation were
15 recorded. The genera of fungi were determined according the above morphologic
16 characteristics (2,8). A total of 120 dishes [2 samples (fallen or aerial leaves), 6
17 dilutions, 5 culture media, and two dishes] were used, and the experiment was
18 conducted in November 2005, August and October 2006, and January 2007. Finally, the
19 number of genera and the frequency at which each genus was isolated were determined
20 for aerial and fallen leaves.

21 **Spore dispersal.** *Volumetric spore traps.* Conidia of *S. oleagina* were quantified
22 with a 7-day volumetric spore trap (Burkard Manufacturing Co. Ltd.) that was placed 1
23 m above ground level in the experimental orchard. The trap was operated from February
24 to April 1994, and the sticky tape that collected the spores was replaced weekly. In the
25 laboratory, the tape was cut into daily segments (48 mm), which were examined every

1 other day. The entire area of each daily segment was scanned with a microscope at ×
2 400 magnifications, and the *S. oleagina* conidia were counted and expressed as the
3 number per week.

4 *Glass microscope slide spore traps.* Glass microscope slides provided a rapid
5 and easy way to quantify *S. oleagina* conidia in olive orchards. Glass microscope slides
6 (26 × 75 mm) coated on both sides with a thin double-sided adhesive (Tanglefoot
7 Company, Grand Rapids, MI) tape (24 × 50 mm) were placed on wooden stakes at 1 m
8 above the ground in the experimental orchard. Eight microscope slides (four in
9 horizontal and four in vertical position) were placed on each stake. Eight stakes were
10 placed 0 (under the olive canopy), 4, 10, or 40 m distant from a highly affected tree. In
11 total, 64 microscope slides were placed per distance from the inoculum source. After 1
12 week, 10.8% of the area of each slide was scanned as described earlier, and the *S.*
13 *oleagina* conidia were counted. The study was carried out five times from November
14 1996 to April 1997.

15 **Data analysis.** Data were analyzed using Statistix 9 (Analytical Software,
16 Tallahassee, FL). The descriptive statistics for the variables (mean, standard deviation,
17 variance, standard error of the mean, minimum, and maximum) were calculated using
18 the summary statistics of the software. Pearson's correlation was used to evaluate the
19 relationships between the number of conidia per cm² of lesion and viability (% of
20 conidia germination). Moreover, the number of viable conidia (number of conidia
21 produced multiplied by their viability) and the number of cumulative viable conidia
22 were determined and plotted on time. We assume that the spores produced in one week
23 are removed each week by rainfall. Because the cumulative number of viable conidia
24 over time approached a maximum level asymptotically, data were fitted using different
25 models of saturation with clear biological meaning (10,13); 22 September (the equinox

1 of autumn) was considered day zero. The best regression model was chosen based on
2 Akaike's information criterion, the coefficient of determination (R^2), and the normal
3 distribution of errors and by examining graphs of the standardized residuals plotted
4 against predicted values. To study the effect of season on the cumulative number of
5 viable conidia per cm^2 of lesion produced over time, we linearized the selected models
6 of each season and compared the regression lines based on their homogeneity of
7 variances, slopes, and intercepts.

8 The effect of date on inoculum density (conidia per cm^2 of lesion) on the leaves
9 that were placed on the soil surface was determined with an analysis of variance
10 (ANOVA). The inoculum density values were logarithmically transformed when it was
11 necessary for homogeneity of variance. The means obtained at different evaluation
12 times were compared using Tukey's honestly significant difference (HSD) test at $P=$
13 0.05. To study the frequency (%) of isolation of other fungal species from olive leaves
14 placed on soil surface or olive canopy, we applied a Fisher's exact test for each fungal
15 species at $P = 0.05$.

16 The relationship between rainfall and density of trapped *S. oleagina* conidia was
17 evaluated by linear regression using an equation forced through the origin. In the linear
18 regression analyses, the following were determined: the significance of the regression,
19 R^2 , the coefficient of determination adjusted for degrees of freedom (R_a^2), and the
20 pattern of residuals. Finally, the power law and different exponential models, which
21 describe the influence of distance from the source of inoculum on density of trapped
22 conidia, were tested (4,5,10). The best model was selected as described above. All of
23 the regression models used in this study were developed with an empirical approach,
24 that is, the form of the model was determined by the collected data (10).

25

RESULTS

1 **Survival on aerial or fallen infected leaves.** The pathogen did not produce new
2 conidia on lesions on leaves placed on the soil surface. In about 5% of the samples that
3 were placed on the soil surface, the pathogen developed a stroma with a
4 pseudoparenchymal spherical tissue similar to immature pseudothecia of *Venturia* spp.
5 or sclerotia, but mature pseudothecia with ascospores or asci were never observed.
6 Likewise, enlarged intercalary cells of hyphae similar to chlamydospores were observed
7 on 10% of the leaves placed on the soil surface. Overall, leaves on the soil were rapidly
8 colonized by saprophytic fungi during the wet periods. The most common of these fungi
9 was *Coleophoma oleae* followed by species of *Alternaria*, *Aureobasidium*,
10 *Cladosporium*, *Epicoccum*, and *Phoma*.

11 The pathogen did not produce new conidia around the lesions (whitish spots) of
12 aerial leaves collected in September 1995, after a summer that was characterized by
13 high temperatures (up to 45°C). The pathogen, however, produced new conidia around
14 the whitish spots in September 1997 after a mild summer.

15 In olive leaves that had wintered on the soil surface and were collected at the end
16 of winter in the main olive-growing areas of Andalusia, the pathogen was not easily
17 detected. No conidia were observed in old scab lesions, and only some pseudothecia-
18 like structures and chlamydospores were observed. As in the experimental orchard, all
19 leaves were colonized by saprophytic fungi, mainly *Coleophoma oleae* and unidentified
20 species of *Alternaria*, *Cladosporium*, *Epicoccum*, *Fusarium*, *Mucor*, *Phoma*, *Rhizopus*,
21 and *Trichoderma*.

22 **Conidial density and viability on aerial and fallen infected leaves.** Different
23 patterns of conidial density of *S. oleagina* on aerial leaves were observed across seasons
24 (Fig. 1). Three of the four seasons (1993/94, 94/95, and 96/97) were favorable for olive
25 scab epidemics, and one season (1995/96) was unfavorable. In 1993/94, the pathogen

1 produced conidia from the end of October until the end of June, although conidial
2 density was not quantified during this first season; germination of conidia ranged from
3 45 to 80% in this season. In 1994/95, conidia were detected from the end of November
4 to July, i.e., the period was 1 month shorter than in the previous season, and conidial
5 germination ranged from 2 to 73%. During this season (1994/95), the pathogen
6 produced $> 1.5 \times 10^5$ conidia cm^{-2} of lesion during the winter with a peak in December
7 and another in February. From February to the end of March, density of *S. oleagina*
8 conidia decreased markedly and remained low ($< 5 \times 10^4$ conidia cm^{-2} of lesion) until
9 July. In the unfavorable season (1995/96), the pathogen produced only a few conidia ($<$
10 2×10^4 conidia cm^{-2} of lesion) on infected leaves from May to mid-July, although most
11 conidia ($> 60\%$) germinated. In the last season studied (1996/97), conidial density was
12 large ($> 1.8 \times 10^5$ conidia cm^{-2} of lesion) from October to December, decreased from
13 December until April (1.4×10^4 conidia cm^{-2} of lesion), and remained low during the
14 spring and summer. In most months of the last season, the percentage of conidial
15 germination was $> 40\%$ with a marked decline in March and another in August. The
16 pathogen did not produce conidia during the summer, with one exception that occurred
17 in 1997, when a few conidia were detected during July and August (Fig. 1).

18 Overall, the number of viable conidia per unit area of lesion was greatest during
19 November–December and decreased gradually from this time until April (Fig. 2A);
20 from April to autumn, this value was zero or near zero. In all cases, the cumulative
21 number of conidia per unit area of lesion through the season (Fig. 2B) was best
22 described by a monomolecular model with the following equation:

$$23 \quad Y = a(1 - e^{-b(t-c)}) \quad (1)$$

1 in which Y = the cumulative number of conidia, a = maximum cumulative number of
2 conidia or asymptote, t = days after 22 September, and b and c represent unknown
3 parameters. The above equation can be linearized as:

$$4 \quad \mathit{Ln}(a - Y) = \mathit{Lna} + bc - bt \quad (2)$$

5 The fitted and linearized models for the three seasons were:

$$6 \quad \mathit{Ln}(a - Y) = 16.702 - 0.034t$$

$$7 \quad \mathit{Ln}(a - Y) = 41.371 - 0.1384t$$

$$8 \quad \mathit{Ln}(a - Y) = 15.600 - 0.0281t$$

9 in 1994/95, 95/96, and 96/97, respectively; in all three seasons, $P < 0.002$ and R^2 and
10 $R^2a > 0.83$. There was a significant ($P = 0.0365$) difference between the slopes (b = the
11 rate of conidia increase) but there were no differences ($P = 0.5855$) between the
12 elevations of the regression lines of favorable seasons (1994/95 and 96/97) for the
13 epidemics. In both seasons, the cumulative number of viable conidia approached a
14 maximum at the end of March (Fig. 2B).

15 The pathogen did not produce conidia on infected leaves that were placed on the
16 soil surface, although the pre-existing conidia were detected on lesions of leaves for up
17 to 12 weeks. The leaves were rapidly colonized by saprophytic fungi, mainly species of
18 *Alternaria*, *Aureobasidium*, and *Cladosporium*, which apparently degraded the leaf
19 tissues. Overall, the number of conidia and their viability decreased after the leaves
20 were placed on the soil surface (Fig. 3). Nevertheless, there were important differences
21 among trials (evaluation periods) because the colonization and degradation of leaf tissue
22 by saprophytic microorganisms was faster when the weather was humid rather than dry.
23 Thus, the cumulate rainfall during the trials of March 1995, September 1996, and April
24 1997, was 29.4, 404.0, and 158.4 mm, respectively. In the first trial, conidium density
25 and germination did not significantly change during the first month ($P > 0.05$) but then

1 decreased markedly (Fig. 3A). In the second trial, the density of *S. oleagina* conidia on
2 the leaf lesions decreased during the first month and remained low during the second
3 month (Fig. 3B). The density of conidia on lesions of the leaves at the beginning of the
4 third trial was around 10 times lower than the density in the previous trials, but a low
5 density of conidia was on the leaves for another 28 days. Although conidial density was
6 relatively constant over time, it did differ ($P = 0.0119$) among evaluation times. During
7 the first month of the third trial, the percentage of conidial germination was high (>
8 70%) and decreased in the following weeks (Fig. 3C). In all three trials, conidial density
9 on lesions was correlated (Pearson test; $P < 0.005$) with the percentage of conidial
10 germination.

11 **Fungal diversity on aerial or fallen infected leaves.** Ten fungal species
12 representing 10 common saprophytic genera were isolated from leaves of the tree
13 canopy, and six species were isolated from fallen leaves (Table 1). Colonies of *S.*
14 *oleagina* were not obtained from both kinds of leaves. Because there were no
15 differences in the percentage of fungal isolations among evaluation times (November
16 2005, August and October 2006, and January 2007), results were combined in Table 1.
17 Among the aerial leaves, *Phoma* sp. was the species most frequently isolated, followed
18 by *Alternaria* sp. Both species were also common on fallen leaves. *Cladosporium* and
19 *Rhizopus* spp. were also isolated from aerial and fallen leaves but they were more
20 frequently isolated from fallen leaves. *Ascochyta* sp., *Aureobasidium* sp., *Coniothyrium*
21 sp., *Fusarium* sp., *Diplodia* sp., and *Ulocladium* sp. were isolated only from aerial
22 leaves. Conversely, *Mucor* sp. and *Trichoderma* sp. were isolated only from fallen
23 leaves (Table 1). Pycnidia and conidia of the fungus *Coleophoma oleae* were observed
24 in most of the fallen leaves and on some aerial leaves that showed necrotic areas, but it

1 was not isolated from the sampled leaves. No fungi isolated during this study produced
2 sexual structures on olive leaves.

3 **Spore dispersal.** *Volumetric spore traps.* Because of their characteristic
4 morphology (shape, size, and color), *S. oleagina* conidia were easily identified on the
5 spore sample tape (and also on leaves and on microscope slides). From February to July
6 1994, however, only 47 *S. oleagina* conidia were trapped on the continuously operated
7 spore sampler tape. In spite of that, there was an important quantity of inoculum during
8 this period in the orchard (*data not shown*). Of the 47 conidia on the spore tape, 42 were
9 attached to the peltate trichomes of olive leaves. In other words, conidia and trichomes
10 became attached to each other and were transported together from the infected leaves to
11 the sampler tape.

12 *Glass microscope slide spore traps.* The number of *S. oleagina* conidia trapped
13 on microscope slides depended greatly on rainfall and distance from the inoculum
14 source (Table 2). There was a positive relationship between the number of conidia
15 trapped and rainfall when the slides were placed directly under the canopy (distance = 0
16 m), at 4 m, and at 10 m of distance from the canopy of a highly infected tree (Table 2).
17 The conidia trapped under the olive canopy ranged between 1130 and 5 conidia per cm²
18 of coverslip during the rainiest (114.0 mm, 13 to 20 of January 1997) and the driest (0
19 mm, from 20 to 27 of March 1997) periods, respectively (Table 2). However, 21-h of
20 leaf wetness was measured in the olive canopy during those dry periods due to the dew.
21 The number of *S. oleagina* conidia trapped was highest under the olive canopy and
22 decreased exponentially with distance from the canopy. Thus, the slides that were
23 located at 40 m trapped only a small number of conidia and only during the two periods
24 with the highest rainfall (> 60 mm). Several linear and nonlinear models were evaluated

1 to describe the effect of distance on dispersal, and best and simplest was the exponential
2 model:

$$3 \quad Y = ae^{-bS} \quad (3)$$

4
5 in which Y =density of trapped conidia (conidia per cm²), S = distance (m) from the
6 source of inoculum, a represents the average density of inoculum under the olive
7 canopy (at $S = 0$), and b is the unknown parameter that represents the slope of the
8 dispersal gradient (m⁻¹). The equation adjusted for the observed data was:

$$9 \quad Y = 396.52e^{-0.4335S}$$

10 The equation's coefficient of determination (R^2) was 0.9890, and standardized residuals
11 were randomly distributed over predicted Y . The relationship between Y and S is
12 described in Figure 4.

13 DISCUSSION

14 In this study, inoculum sources and patterns of production and dispersal of *S.*
15 *oleagina* conidia were evaluated under field conditions in the Andalusia region of
16 southern Spain, which is the largest (> 1.5 million hectares) olive-growing region in the
17 world (9). Because the pathogen evidently did not produce conidia on the fallen leaves,
18 the most important inoculum source was determined to be the infected leaves that
19 remain in the tree canopy. Our data indicated, however, that high temperature during the
20 summer limits the viability of *S. oleagina* conidia on the aerial leaves. Infected leaves of
21 cultivated olives and wild olives (*Olea europaea* subsp. *europaea* var. *sylvestris*) are
22 considered the only inoculum sources because *S. oleagina* is an obligate parasite and is
23 specific to these hosts (28). Other authors have suggested that infected fallen leaves are
24 an important inoculum source but they did not provide any epidemiological evidence to
25 support this claim (17,20,46). Although our results indicate that fallen leaves are not an
26 inoculum source, we cannot exclude the possibility that they might function as an

1 inoculum source with different weather conditions, different populations of the
2 pathogen, or different saprophytic microorganisms.

3 Olive leaves that fall to the ground are usually soon decomposed by saprophytic
4 fungi and bacteria and also by soil fauna. Thus, Miller (25) indicated that conidial
5 production by *S. oleagina* on fallen leaves is markedly influenced by the saprophytic
6 fungi in the soil. In our study, species of *Phoma* and *Coleophoma oleae* were the most
7 frequent fungi on aerial and fallen leaves, respectively. According to Hudson (19),
8 species of both genera are common on senescent leaves as saprophytic or secondary
9 contaminants. *Alternaria* spp. were also frequently isolated from aerial and fallen
10 leaves. Several species of *Alternaria* are mostly saprophytic, although *A. alternata* has
11 been described as a pathogen of olive fruit (29). In our study, the decomposition of leaf
12 tissue was faster during the wet than the periods, which is consistent with previous
13 observations of olive leaves (19) and which is consistent with the very large body of
14 literature on litter decomposition (7).

15 Sexual fruiting bodies of *S. oleagina* were not observed in this study or in previous
16 research done in California (25), Italy (15), or Morocco (17). The pathogen, however,
17 did develop a pseudoparenchymal spherical tissue similar to immature pseudothecia of
18 *Venturia* spp. in the current study. Likewise, D'Oliveria and D'Oliveria (11) observed
19 immature pseudothecia of *S. eryobotryae* on loquat leaves but were unable to confirm
20 the occurrence of sexual reproduction on that host. Because *S. oleagina* does not
21 develop sexual fruiting bodies, its ability to survive in fallen leaves is limited.
22 Pathogens similar to *S. oleagina* such as species of *Venturia* (anamorphs:
23 *Cladosporium*, *Fusicladium*, and *Spilocaea*) overwinter predominantly as pseudothecia
24 (sexual fruiting bodies) that develop in leaves after their abscission (23,39). Thus,
25 pseudothecia are found more frequently in Venturiaceae species that are pathogenic on

1 deciduous tree species, such as apple (*Malus*), ash (*Fraxinus*), birch (*Betula*), cherry
2 (*Prunus*), nectarine (*Prunus*), European and Asian pear (*Pyrus*), and peach (*Prunus*)
3 (23,38,39) than in Venturiaceae species that affect evergreen trees, including firethorn
4 (*Pyracantha*), loquat (*Eriobotrya*), and olive (15,21,37). Again, this is true because
5 pathogens in the latter group are always associated with living leaves (33).

6 Several authors have described two peaks of conidial production by *S. oleagina*
7 (one in November–December and another in March–April) in Italy (32), Morocco (14),
8 and Turkey (6). Under our conditions, levels of viable inoculum were highest from mid-
9 November to mid-December, although we have evaluated the density of conidia on
10 lesion not the total production of conidia. Besides conidial density and viability, the
11 available inoculum also depends of disease incidence and severity, which reach the
12 highest values on February-March in Andalusia (43,44). The elevated temperatures
13 during the spring in Córdoba Province and the susceptibility of olive cv. Picual would
14 help explain the differences between our results and those of the other authors. In our
15 study, the highest conidial density occurred several weeks before bud break. At this
16 time, however, the olive tree has only mature leaves, which have ontogenic resistance to
17 infection by the pathogen (31,45). In the northern hemisphere, the period for olive leaf
18 growth lasts from March to mid-July; a second and less important flush may occur
19 between September and mid-October, which coincides with the early autumn rains or
20 irrigation applications (9). The weather conditions (temperature from 15 to 20°C and
21 wetness duration > 24 h) and the presence of developing leaves during early spring are
22 usually adequate for leaf infection in olive-growing areas in the southern Spain
23 (31,36,45). In Andalusia Region, from March to April is the main infection period due
24 to the presence of developing leaves of olive, *S. oleagina* conidia, and rainfall; although
25 infections can also occur during late spring and autumn (42). However, treatments with

1 copper-based fungicides during the winter, before bud break, will be useful if there is a
2 significant number of conidia in leaf lesions because copper-based fungicides reduce the
3 viability of *S. oleagina* conidia (34,35). Such an approach has been validated
4 experimentally (34,35,43) and is now a standard recommendation for producers (41).
5 Treatments with copper-based fungicides are essential during the autumn for control of
6 anthracnose, caused by *Colletotrichum* spp., in olive orchards where susceptible
7 cultivars such as ‘Galega vulgar’, ‘Hojiblanca’, or ‘Picudo’ are grown (26,27).

8 In addition to being affected by leaf maturity and inoculum potential, risk of leaf
9 infection by *S. oleagina* is also conditioned by rainfall. Conidia spread in splashing
10 water are deposited on the leaf surface and will then infect and cause symptoms if
11 temperature is favorable and leaf tissues are susceptible to infection (40,46). Previous
12 spore-trapping studies in olive orchards in Italy showed that *S. oleagina* conidia are
13 mainly spread as airborne inoculum during periods of rainfall (22,24). These studies
14 have also demonstrated that a small number of conidia can also be spread by wind alone
15 for at least 20 m from the inoculum source (22). Conidia can also be transported by the
16 insect *Ectopsocus briggsi* (24). Because the number of conidia trapped close to the
17 inoculum source (< 40 m) was linearly and positively related with the cumulative
18 rainfall, our results strongly indicate that *S. oleagina* is water-splash dispersed and for
19 only short distances. The number of dispersed conidia decreased exponentially with
20 increasing distance from the inoculum source. A small number of *S. oleagina* conidia
21 were trapped beneath the olive tree canopy during the dry period, suggesting that dew
22 may enable a limited degree of vertical dissemination of conidia within the canopy of
23 the olive tree. Using volumetric spore trapping, we observed that some conidia were
24 associated with the leaf trichomes. The peltate trichomes of olive leaves resemble
25 umbrellas and might act like parachutes and thereby enhance conidia dispersal. This

1 may explain how the disease spreads from one olive grove to another given that wind
2 and rain alone do not result in substantial dispersal for distances > 20 m (24).

3 The most widely used empirical models for describing the relationship between
4 spore dispersal and distance from a source of inoculum are the power law model and
5 simple exponential models (10). Fitt *et al.* (14) compared both models and concluded
6 that they had limitations, although the exponential model can be more easily
7 incorporated into models of disease development than the power law model because the
8 boundary condition at the source is finite rather than infinite. In our case, the data for
9 number of conidia trapped with increasing distance from an affected olive tree were
10 better described by the exponential model than the power law model, which was in
11 agreement with the results of a previous study (22). Overall, when pathogens are rain-
12 splash dispersed, the exponential model may be a better fit than the power law model
13 (10).

14 Although this study of *S. oleagina* has documented patterns of conidial production
15 and dispersion and previous studies established the factors affecting infection of leaves
16 (31,45), more detailed examination of the temporal progress of the disease is needed to
17 identify cultivar and environmental factors that determine epidemic development. Such
18 information should support the design of a disease forecasting system for the proper
19 timing of fungicide treatments.

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ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

22 J. R. Viruega and J. Moral contributed equally to this article. This research was
23 supported by projects AGF93-0342 and AGF96-1082 from the CICYT, the Spanish
24 Ministry of Education and Science (MEC), and project AGR-03635 from DGPA,
25 Andalusia Regional Government. Juan Moral is the holder a Juan de la Cierva Post-Doc

1 grant from MEC. We thank F. Luque for her valuable technical assistance and C. M.
2 Díez, D. Gramaje, B. Jaffe, and W. J. Kaiser for critical review of the manuscript.

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TABLE 1. Fungal genera isolated from *Spilocaea oleagina*-infected olive leaves in the tree canopy or on the soil surface of an olive orchard cv. Picual in the Andalusia region of southern Spain.

Genus	Olive leaves with indicated fungi (%) ^a		
	Tree canopy	Soil surface	Total
<i>Phoma</i>	51.3	14.3 ^{*b}	45.4
<i>Alternaria</i>	12.0	21.4	13.6
<i>Rhizopus</i>	4.0	28.5 [*]	7.9
<i>Cladosporium</i>	5.4	14.3 [*]	6.8
<i>Ascochyta</i>	6.7	0 [*]	5.7
<i>Aureobasidium</i>	6.7	0 [*]	5.7
<i>Coniothyrium</i>	5.4	0 [*]	4.5
<i>Fusarium</i>	5.4	0 [*]	4.5
<i>Mucor</i>	0	14.3 [*]	2.2
<i>Diplodia</i>	1.3	0	1.1
<i>Trichoderma</i>	0	7.1 [*]	1.1
<i>Ulocladium</i>	1.3	0	1.1

^aValues are means of four repetitions, with 100 leaves per repetition.

^bWithin each row, an asterisk indicates a significant difference ($P < 0.05$) between leaves in the tree canopy vs. leaves on the soil surface (according to the Fisher's exact test).

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TABLE 2. The relationship between density of trapped *Spilocaea oleagina* conidia on microscope slides and distance from a highly affected olive tree.

Time period	Rainfall (mm) ^a	Number of trapped conidia (per cm ² of slide) at four distances from a highly infected tree			
		0 m ^b	4 m	10 m	40 m
13-20 January 1997	114.0	1129.80	24.59	0.41	0.09
06-13 December 1996	68.0	549.00	8.62	0.29	0.05
17-24 April 1997	17.6	154.03	2.22	0.05	0.00
15-22 November 1996	4.0	144.68	0.06	0.00	0.00
20-27 March 1997	0.0	5.11	0.00	0.00	0.00
Linear Regression^c		$Y = 9.440X$	$Y = 0.191X$	$Y = 0.004X$	-
R²		0.9858	0.9579	0.9921	-
P		<0.0001	<0.0001	<0.0001	-

^aCumulative rainfall (mm) during 7 days

^bThe conidial traps were placed under the olive canopy (0 m) or at 4, 10, or 40 m from the canopy.

^cLinear regression equation for density of trapped conidia (Y) vs. rainfall (X); the coefficient of determination (R^2) and significance (P) of the regressions are also indicated.

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2 **FIGURE LEGENDS**
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5 **Fig. 1.** Germination and density of *Spilocaea oleagina* conidia produced on non-fallen,
6 infected olive leaves. The infected leaves, which were collected from the tree canopy in
7 the Andalusia region of southern Spain during four seasons, were incubated in the
8 laboratory. During the season 1994/95, only conidial germination was measured. Values
9 for conidial density are the means of 120 replicate leaves, and values for conidial
10 germination are the means of 400 conidia. Bars represent the standard error of the mean.
11

12 **Fig. 2.** Density of viable conidia of *Spilocaea oleagina* produced on infected olive
13 leaves. The infected leaves showing scab lesions were collected from the tree canopy in
14 Andalusia region of southern Spain through three seasons (1994/95, 95/96, and 96/97).
15 (A) Density on each sampling date. (B) Cumulative density. Values are the means of
16 120 leaves, and bars represent the standard error of the mean.
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18 **Fig. 3.** Germination and density of *Spilocaea oleagina* conidia produced on infected
19 olive leaves that were placed on the soil surface beneath the olive canopy in the
20 Andalusia region of southern Spain during three growing seasons: (A) 1994/95,
21 (B)1995/1996, and (C) 1996/1997. Values for conidial density are the mean of 120
22 leaves, and values for germination are the mean of 400 conidia. Bars represent the
23 standard error of the mean. Values for density with the same letter are not significantly
24 different according to Fisher's protected HSD test at $P = 0.05$.
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26 **Fig. 4.** The relationship between the number of *Spilocaea oleagina* conidia trapped per
27 cm^2 of microscope slide and distance from the inoculum source. The curve represents
28 the exponential model ($Y=396.52e^{-0.4335S}$) relating density of trapped conidia [Y

- 1 (conidia/cm²)] to distance (S) from the inoculum source. Values are the observed means
- 2 of 320 microscope slides. The equation fit the observed data with $R^2 = 0.9890$.

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Figure 1

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Figure 2

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Figure 4